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Content-Based Image Retrieval Using Wavelets

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Abstract: - This paper presents a novel approach for content-based image retrieval (CBIR) that provides the analysis of visual information using wavelet coefficients and similarity metrics. This approach has a better performance than well-known RedNew CBIR system based on image indexing and retrieval using neural networks. A principal goal of this report is precise analysis of the four families of wavelets and three techniques for computing similarity. The best Symlet transform and similarity metrics based on Euclidian distance have been adopted in a proposed system called Image Retrieval by Wavelet Coefficients IRWC. In order to test a proposed system the recall and precision metrics used for evaluating the performance of CBIR facilities have been used on base of the standard COIL-100 image collections. The obtained results show the increment of retrieval efficiency up to 92% without additional increasing a processing time. Therefore a proposed approach may be considered as a good alternative for design of new CBIR systems.

Key-Words: - Image processing, visual information retrieval, similarity metrics, wavelets

1 Introduction

In well-known content-based image retrieval systems the extraction of image features is the principal procedure used for image indexing and interpretation [1], [2]. There are a lot of reports about novel approaches and methods for searching, retrieval, indexing, and classification of visual information on base of analysis of low-level image features, such as a color, texture, shape, etc. [3].

These methods sometimes are slow and too complex for design of real-time applications. Additionally, CBIR systems use only low-level feature vectors, which do not provide mechanisms to represent a meaning of images. Another significant problem of image retrieval process is computing similarity between feature vectors of visual query and images, which are candidates to be retrieved. The comparison of the feature vectors without their adjustment and normalization frequently is not fast and convenient way to find the matching between them. That is why the feature vectors must be converted to other domains for simple and efficient image characteristics extraction, indexing, and classification [5].

Among the commercial CBIR systems that may be used as prototypes for development of novel retrieval techniques, CIRES (Content Based Image REtrieval System) is the one of efficient facilities that provides features retrieval, such as a structure, color, and texture of image combining them with

user specifications of importance of these features in a query [2].

SIMPLIcity (Semantics-sensitive Integrated Matching for Picture Libraries) provides image retrieval from the Web using texture, indexing by clustering of image segments, and feature vectors is generated by wavelets transform [6]. Another CBIR facility for classification of segmented images combining neural networks and wavelet matching is known as RedNew system [7]. This system provides a region growing using multiresolution in YIQ color domain applying Jacobs' metrics for computing similarity between retrieved images and visual query.

After testing this system some its disadvantages have been detected, such as a low percentage of relevant retrieved images and necessity of training the neural net for new classes of visual information. In this research we propose to apply a novel approach for RedNew CBIR systems improving as low-level features extraction process as semantic aspect of retrieved images.

This paper is presented in the following manner: in the section II the analysis of methods related with CBIR and RedNew system are presented. The section III shows the conceptual basis of the proposed approach and selection of the best wavelet transforms and similarity metrics. The testing and evaluation of proposed approach and designed IRWC system are presented in sections IV.

2 Related Approaches and RedNew

Among the image features the most important are color and shape because they define the specific regions in image which may be interpreted and classified as the objects with certain significance in a scene. The main purpose of image retrieval system is its content extraction that permits to choose the relevant information to user's visual query as it done now in well-known searching engine based on textual description. In this case the shape or region representing the objects has a meaning by itself and may be used as a principal feature in CBIR. However a shape or region matching is considered as one of the most difficult aspects of image processing due to they need a lot of parameters to be indexed, classified, and represented explicitly. The well known methods for global color/shape/region description such as Elasticity correspondence [8], Curvature scale space approach [9], B-splines and chain case codes [5], Two-Segment Turning function and Star field approaches [1], Fourier spectral descriptors [10], etc. sometimes are too complex for fast non-sensible to spatial variations processing and frequently they do not provide the efficient feature extraction.

After the analysis of well-known methods, some of them have been selected taking into account their performance and usefulness for improving the CBIR process, particularly, the characteristics, such as processing speed, high grade of similarity with input visual query, low number of iteration in retrieved process, and simplicity in description of image semantics. One of the approaches with the mentioned characteristics is based on applying wavelet transforms because they provide a high grade of relevance of retrieved images, extracts image features in noised images, and sometimes they are invariant to spatial distortions in image [11].

The selected CBIR facility, which may be improved applying a novel retrieval approach, is RedNew system presented in Fig. 1. The system consists of two channels: one of them generates wavelets characteristics of the input querying image and another one retrieves the centroid images from preprocessed image collection during their comparison. The centroid is the generalized image representing the class or group of images in collection with similar content providing in this way the distribution of the images in collection on base of their semantic features. This process of distribution of images and organization of collection is made by using the ART2 neural net. It assigns to set of image parameters the corresponding values that define to which group this image belongs, for

example, to group of buildings, maps, animals, landscapes, etc.

Fig. 1. Block diagram of RedNew CBIR system.

The structure of the net has 16 nodes on input layer for each hidden layer with dynamically generated nodes during training process, and 12 nodes on output layer. When the collection of images is classified in semantic groups the retrieval process may be started. For each classified image in the group wavelet coefficients are computed, and then the feature vector (centroid) for each particular group are defined. The centroid is generated by calculation of average value of wavelet coefficients for particular group and then this value is normalized to scale from 0 to 1. This process is applied to all images in collection and, using Euclidian distance metrics as square root of difference between the squares of the computed for each image average values, the classification of the images is provided. However these centroids do not express the general means of the images in group, they show how similar is one image to other in collection taking into account only low-level image characteristics defined in feature vector. That is why the user feedback is needed to define the semantics of each image with user-oriented indexing vocabulary for description of the scenes in these images.

The image analysis and retrieval processes include four steps: preprocessing, corresponding centroid generation, matching computing between centroids, and retrieval of images with high grade of similarity. The input querying image is divided in regions applying YIQ multiresolution decomposition and then sixteen features that compose the feature vector, such as region area, its maximum radius and luminosity, RGB average, elliptical envelope, moments, etc. are computed for each region. The input visual query that may be thumbnail image, sketch, or shape is converted to its feature vector and then the computing similarity is provided by

matching of this vector with all centroids in collection. The highest grade of similarity between two vectors defines the group of images that may be candidates for retrieval. This grade is computed according the procedure proposed by Jacobs [11].

$$\|Q, T\| = w_{(0,0)}|Q[0,0] - T[0,0]| + \sum_{j,j} w_{(i,j)}|\tilde{Q}[i,j] - \tilde{T}[i,j]| \quad (1)$$

where Q represent the feature vector of the querying image and T is the centroid corresponding to compared particular class of image collection, $w_{(i,j)}$ is a semantic weight associated with a class of images to which centroid belongs in T . When the best correspondence with one or more centroids is found the comparison of the wavelet characteristics of images within the selected class is applied to find those images that have the highest grade of similarity to low-level image features. Thus, a system has two steps of matching: first one consists in selection of a class due to analysis of similar content of compared images, and second one includes a selection of the most similar images within the class on base low-level features.

The disadvantage of the proposed approach implemented in RedNew system is a significant time that it takes for collection organization, which additionally requires the user's feedback description of images. There is another waste of time due to a long process of the feature vector generation. We determined empirically that this time is about some seconds for retrieval of images from collection which has 7200 images processed on personal computer of 2GHz and RAM of 1GB [12]. Additionally, if a new querying image that has not the corresponding similar preprocessed images in collection, the approach is failed retrieving usually

nonsense information. In this case the collection must be updated with a new image generating a new semantic class and the training of the neural net has to be applied for definition of a centroid corresponding to this class. The performance of the RedNew may be improved by a novel approach implemented in proposed IRWC system.

3 Proposed IRWC System Design

The proposed approach may be described the block diagram of the designed IRWC system shown in Fig.2. It adopts the principal concepts of RedNew system but the sequence of data processing is different that reduces the complexity of the used in RedNew algorithms without increment of computational cost. The modifications of implemented IRWC system includes simplification of the preprocessing steps where only YIQ color decomposition of image is applied. The neural network is substituted by wavelet transform for generation of characteristics to be compared. That is why the computing similarity does not use the centroid of images. In order to select the best type of the wavelet transform, the four approaches for generation of feature vectors have been implemented, particularly, Haar, Daubechines, Biorthogonal wavelet, and Symlet transforms. These four different wavelet approaches are tested in this system and the best one is selected for final version of IRWC. The advantages of wavelet approaches comparing them with other feature extraction methods consist in better convergence of results, symmetry, and regularity useful for image processing with presence of noise [7].

Fig. 2. IRWC system for image retrieval using wavelet characteristics.

The first simplest way for multiresolution analysis is applying Haar wavelet transform that may be defined by the following equations:

$$\begin{aligned} \psi(x) &= 1, & \text{if } 0 \leq x \leq 0.5 \\ \psi(x) &= -1, & \text{if } 0.5 < x \leq 1.0 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where $\psi(x)$ is Haar transform and x is an input querying image. The other one is Daubechines transform that belongs to family of discrete orthogonal wavelets computed as it shown

$$Daubechies_{(y)} = \sum_{k=0}^{N-1} C_k^{N-1+k} y^k \quad (3)$$

where C_k^{N-1+k} denotes binomial coefficients, N is a size of processed set and y is the input pixel. The third approach to be evaluated is Biorthogonal transform. It is efficient for image reconstruction applying the equation

$$Biort_{j,k} = \int s(x) \tilde{\psi}_{j,k}(x) dx \quad (4)$$

where j and k are coordinates of the pixels in input image, $\tilde{\psi}_{j,k}(x)$ is Haar wavelet transform obtained from equation (2), and $s(x)$ is defined as first derivative of image x . The last one is the Symlet transform similar to Daubechines wavelet but it provides the best symmetry and may be obtained by the following equation

$$Symlet_{(X)} = e^{\varphi(i)\omega} \quad (5)$$

where x is input image, $\varphi(i)$ is Daubechines transform for each pixel i , and ω is the moment of an image. The results of the extraction the wavelet characteristics for mentioned four transforms are shown in Fig. 3. The length of feature vector and the level of decomposition in each transform are presented in Table 1. All vectors have a similar decomposition ability limited by noise that they generate, and significant length of feature vector provides more precise comparison during matching process.

Table 1. Feature vectors characteristics

Wavelet type	Decomposition	Feature vector size
Haar	5.0	1x4096
Daubechines	4.0	1x4489
Biorthogonal	6.8	1x5184
Symlet	4.0	1x4489

The last step of image retrieval process is a computing similarity between the feature vector of input image obtained after applying the four wavelet transforms and the vectors of previously preprocessed images in collection.

Fig. 3. Wavelet coefficients extraction a) Haar, b) Daubechines, c) Biorthogonal, d) Symlet transforms

In this research we propose to use some techniques for computing similarity in order to define which one provides reliable results. First one is a similarity metrics based on Jacobs' equation (1) we used in RedNew system. This equation has been modified in the following manner to use it with wavelet coefficients of IRWC system, such as

$$\|Q, T\| = |Q[0,0] - T[0,0]| + \sum_{i,j} |\tilde{Q}[i,j] - \tilde{T}[i,j]| \quad (6)$$

where Q and T represent the features of a querying image and images in collection respectively. The comparison is implemented in the following way: if the coefficients for particular feature are similar $Q(i,j) = T(i,j)$, the accumulative similarity metrics for these vectors is incremented, otherwise it is not modified. The maximum accumulative value of metrics for each pair of compared vectors is

considered as the basic measure for retrieval. Second metrics is based on Euclidian distance between the feature vectors, particularly, between wavelet characteristics applying the following equation:

$$\|P, Q\| = \sqrt{(p_x - q_x)^2 + (p_y - q_y)^2} \quad (7)$$

where P and Q represent the wavelet characteristics of preprocessed image from collection and input querying image respectively.

Q.Tian metrics frequently used for computing similarity $S_j(f_i)$ may be obtained applying next equation [13]

$$S_j(f_i) = (x_i - q_i)^T (x_i - q_i) \quad (8)$$

where x_i is the i -th vector of the j -th image within a collection and q_i is the i -th vector of querying image, $(x_i - q_i)^T$ is the transposed response of the difference $(x_i - q_i)$. These three metrics have been tested in IRWC system as it described in the next section and the best one has been selected for final version.

4 Experiments and Discussion

For analyzing the performance of the wavelet transforms and similarity metrics we divide experiments in two groups. First one is *Candidate Images Selected by Different Similarity Metrics* experiment, which consists in applying Jacobs', Euclidian, and Q.Tian metrics over the sets of previously classified images in collections (Columbia Object Image Library collection COIL_100) [14]. The purpose of this experiment is to observe how well the used techniques for computing similarity are able to choose the relevant images from collection. In the Table 2 the results of experiments for selected four wavelet transforms using three different matching techniques are presented. Each experiment consisted of random selection of 100 querying images form 72 different classes in collection of 7200 images used for RedNew system.

Table 2. Average values of relevant retrieved images for different wavelets and similarity metrics

Wavelets	Jacobs	Euclidian	Q.Tian	Average for transform,%
Haar	89	91	88	89.3
Daubechines	95	95	89	93.0
Biorthogonal	96	95	88	93.0
Symlet	96	97	91	94.0
Average for metrics,%	94.0	94.5	89.0	

The best performance, presented in bold, has the Symlet transform due to its property of symmetry. The best similarity metrics was the Euclidian distance due to more precise comparison of each characteristic in feature vectors. That is why the Symlet transform and Euclidian similarity metrics have been adopted in proposed IRWC system. In Fig. 4 the GUI of the IRWC system is presented where the relevant retrieves images are shown in downward order.

The second *Candidate Relevant Images* experiment consists in evaluation of the retrieval process in proposed system. The evaluation of CBIR system is non-trivial task. This is because there is an amount of subjectivity involved into query interpretation by user. The similarity between a query and a set of retrieved image depends on individual perception of user. Nevertheless, there is a standard way of judging the obtained results. This technique consists in calculation of two metrics, such as recall and precision. Recall measures the ability of a system to retrieve relevant information from all image collection, and precision is the proportion of the number of relevant retrieved images to the total number of relevant ones in collection. They may be computed according the following equation.

$$PRECISION = \frac{A}{B}, \quad RECALL = \frac{A}{C} \quad (9)$$

where A is a set of relevant images retrieved by system, B is a set of relevant and irrelevant images retrieved by system for particular query, and C is a set of all relevant images in collection for particular query. Table 3 shows the average recall and precision for experiment when randomly selected images from COIL_100 collection are used as querying images for RedNew and IRWC systems.

Fig. 4 The GUI of proposed IRWC system

Table 3. The recall/precision for RedNew and IRWC

RedNew		IRWC	
Recall	Precision	Recall	Precision
0.25	0.83	0.32	1.0
0.15	0.42	0.27	0.85
0.05	0.16	0.32	0.9
0.2	0.95	0.32	0.95
Average 16.25%	Average 60%	Average 31%	Average 92.5%

In RedNew for different sets of images the recall/precision values lie in the intervals about of $(0.05 \div 0.25) / (0.16 \div 1.0)$. In IRWC system the average recall/precision have higher values, which lie in the range of $(0.27 \div 0.32) / (0.85 \div 1.0)$ respectively.

The increment of the recall/precision is obtained by using the Symlet transform with Euclidian distance similarity metrics (up to 92% of relevant retrieved images). In this way RedNew system has been improved incrementing its efficiency for relevant images retrieval and decreasing the number of iterations for searching of necessary visual information.

5 Conclusion

The evaluation of the proposed approach and testing of the designed IRWC system show that ability of system to retrieve relevant information from all image collection is better. It is possible to achieve up to 92% of efficiency in retrieval of images from semantically similar classes. Satisfactory retrieval of expected images is provided faster due to the lower number of iterations in a searching process.

The disadvantages of the system are the presence of errors during wavelet transform and the restrictions for input visual queries, which must have small number of well-defined and separated objects. Additionally, significant occlusions between objects, weak borders or complex background in image are not recommended in this application. The analysis of factors like tolerance to occlusion and deformation, robustness against noise, and feasibility of indexing are considered as possible extension of the proposed approach.

From the obtained experimental results we can conclude that the approach could be considered as an alternative way for the development of visual information retrieval facilities.

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